

**EFFECTIVENESS OF PROJECT KALINGA (KARUNUNGAN LINANGIN
NGAYON) IN ENHANCING THE READING COMPREHENSION IN
FILIPINO OF GRADE 7 STUDENTS**

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Effectiveness of Project KALINGA (Karunungan Linangin Ngayon) in Enhancing the Reading Comprehension in Filipino of Grade 7 Students

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Abstract

This study which focused on the effectiveness of Project KALINGA (Karunungan Linangin Ngayon) in enhancing the reading comprehension in Filipino of Grade 7 students at Marciana P. Catolos National High School. Descriptive method of research was used utilizing the validated pre-test and post-test. Thirty (30) Grade 7 learners who were under frustration level of reading served as the respondents in this research. The findings showed that the learners manifested significant increase in their reading comprehension skills in Filipino after being exposed in Project KALINGA. This means that the program contributed to the improvement of the skills of the target learners. It was concluded that the school-based programs like Project KALINGA is effective initiative in improving the performance of the students particularly in reading.

Keywords: *enhancing, reading comprehension, students*

Introduction

The process of deriving meaning from text is known as reading comprehension. Therefore, rather than trying to deduce meaning from individual words or sentences, the objective is to acquire a general understanding of what is described in the text. Children create mental models, or representations, of the concepts in the text as they read it in order to comprehend the information they are reading (Wooley, 2011).

It is a skill that is critical to the educational success of all individuals. Without adequate reading comprehension, students can struggle in many subject areas. Reading comprehension is an important skill needed for all areas of school.

As readers mature in their comprehension skills, they can progress efficiently from the stage of learning to read to the ultimate goal of reading to learn (Yovanoff, Duesbery, Alonzo, & Tindal, 2005).

The Philippines' Department of Education (DepEd) aims to develop functional literacy in Filipino students. Filipino, as a national language, is essential in promoting cultural identity and unity. Research on reading comprehension in Filipino thus supports this educational goal by identifying ways to strengthen students' abilities to understand, interpret, and analyze Filipino texts, contributing to higher literacy rates nationwide.

It is stated in Department of Education Order No. 14, series of 2018 also known as Policy Guidelines on the Administration of the Revised Philippine Informal Reading Inventory that: "Literacy improvement is one of the priorities of the Department of Education. It is anchored on the flagship program of the department "Every Child A Reader Program" which aims to make every Filipino child a reader and a writer at his/her grade level".

However, reading, specifically comprehension, has been seen as a perennial problem in literacy. In Marciana P. Catolos National High School, specifically in Grade 7, the learners' performance in subject areas is affected by their reading ability as seen in the results of their quizzes and tests. Based on initial observations during reading classes, learners have difficulty answering questions posed after reading the texts.

In addition, the result of the pre-assessment of the reading level of the learners using the Phil-IRI, there are thirty (30) students who are categorized under the frustration reading level. This means that they find the reading materials so difficult that they cannot successfully respond to them. Alos, these learners need extensive assistance from their teacher.

The study of Villanueva & Santos (2019) emphasized the need for individualized reading materials and assessment-driven interventions. It concluded that consistent remedial sessions could bridge the gap between struggling readers and their peers.

Moreover, Reyes (2019) explored the impact of the "Read to Succeed" program, a remedial reading program implemented in selected public schools. The program used story-based instruction, comprehension question drills, and vocabulary activities. Results indicated improvements in both reading fluency and comprehension among struggling readers, with recommendations for integrating similar programs in schools with high dropout rates.

The related readings clearly explained the importance of conducting school-based programs which will provide intervention to the learners who are struggling with their reading comprehension.

Hence, the researcher opted to conduct this study to determine the effectiveness of Project KALINGA in enhancing the comprehension skills in Filipino of Grade 7 learners at Marciana P. Catolos National High School.

Innovation, Intervention, and Strategy

Learning is real gold that must be worked hard to acquire and serve as wealth. Although we are Filipino, many of our students are still weak in the Filipino subject, more than that, they are weak in reading and understanding, add grammar and rhetoric. Moreover, it is not unknown to us that students have laziness and lack of interest in reading, especially in the field of literature. This is a big challenge for Filipino subject teachers. This is the cause of the desire of the Filipino department of Marciana P. Catolos National High School to carry out a project that will help for the development of the wisdom of the students. Using effective methods, we will surely get the desired success.

In this regard, the project KA-LI-NGA: KARungung LINangin NGAYon was formed, so that students can love the subject of Filipino to develop their ability and skills in reading and understanding which is required for monitoring especially those who have deficiencies in reading and understanding the lessons.

The goals of the KA-LI-NGA: KARUNUNGU LINANGIN NGAYON project include: a) make students aware of the importance of reading and its benefits; b) help students in lessons in which they are struggling; and c) increase the level of ability of students in the field of reading and understanding.

This project will be carried out after the initial reading and assess the students and identify the students who need protection, (students who cannot read, have difficulty reading and do not want to read). and will continue until the four marks, once, a week for a month, so that teachers can determine what will help for the development of the student's knowledge. In relation to this, the teacher will prepare lessons that should be given more importance and will be more helpful to the students' learning. The lessons prepared by the teachers are localized self-compositions to be used in reading that match the reading ability of the students. These localized devices can also be used for home visits as well as online distance learning lessons if needed.

Action Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the effectiveness of Project KALINGA on the reading comprehension of Grade 7 learners at Marciana P. Catolos National High School. Specifically, it sought answers to the following research questions.

1. What is the level of performance in terms of their reading comprehension in Filipino before and after being exposed to Project KALINGA as revealed by their pre-test and post-test results?
2. Is there a significant difference between the performance of the student-respondents before and after being exposed to Project KALINGA as revealed by their pre-test and post-test results?

Methodology

Research Design

Descriptive method of research was used in this study. This was the suitable method since its main goal was to determine the effectiveness of Project KALINGA in enhancing the reading comprehension in Filipino of students.

The level of performance of the students was assessed using the pre-test. Then, they were being exposed to Project KALINGA. After which, pos-test was given to determine their level of performance after their exposure to the project.

Participants

Thirty (30) Grade 7 learners served as the respondents of this study. These are those who were categorized under frustration level of reading based on the results of the Phil-IRI. Likewise, total enumeration was being used in choosing the respondents since the program was intended to provided intervention to the learners who were struggling with their reading comprehension skill in Filipino.

Moreover, validated pre-test and post-test were used to gather the necessary data. These were utilized to assess the level of performance of the learners before and after exposure to Project KALINGA.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. *Level of Performance in terms of the Reading Comprehension in Filipino of Grade 7 Students*

Performance of Control Group	Pretest		Posttest	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Outstanding (O)	0	0.00	2	6.67
Very Satisfactory (VS)	0	0.00	12	40.00
Satisfactory (S)	11	36.67	13	43.33
Fairly Satisfactory (FS)	17	56.67	3	10.00
Did Not Meet Expectation (DE)	2	6.67	0	0.00
Total	30	100.00	30	100.00

It was shown in the table that majority of the respondents performed fairly satisfactory as seen in the frequency of 17 out of 30 or 56.67% of the population. The highest level is satisfactory with 11 or 36.67% participants. Thus, after utilizing the Project KALINGA, the number of participants with fairly satisfactory level reduced to 3 or 10%. Also, 12 very satisfactory and 2 outstanding students were produced.

This means that conventional teaching for control group was slightly improved the level of performance in reading comprehension in Filipino of Grade 7 learners.

Table 2. *Significant Difference on the Level of Performance in terms of the Reading Comprehension in Filipino of Grade 7 Students*

Test	n	Mean	SD	Computed t Value	Critical t value ($\alpha=5\%,df=29$)	Decision	Interpretation
Pretest	30	11.07	2.50	7.27	2.05	Reject the Ho	Significant
Posttest	30	17.07	4.18				

It can be seen in the table that the computed t value of 7.27 is greater than the critical t value of 2.05 at 0.05 level of significance and 29 degrees of freedom to conclude that there is a significant difference in the pretest and posttest score of the participants from the control group. The statement is justified that after utilizing the conventional teaching, the number of participants with fairly satisfactory level decreased to 3 out of 30 but 12 very satisfactory and 2 outstanding students were produced. It implied that Project KALINGA helped in the improvement of the level of performance in reading comprehension in Filipino of Grade 7 learners.

Action Plan

Activities	Persons Involved	Date	Success Indicators
Planning and Meeting	School Head Proponent Teachers	October 2024	- Plan of Action
Profiling of the Students	Proponent	October 2024	- List of Respondents
Development of Pre-test and Pos-test	Proponent Students	September 2024	- Pre-test and Post-test
Administration of Pre-test	Proponent	September 2024	- Results of Pre-test
Implementation of Project KALINGA	Proponent Students	September- November 2024	- Narrative and Pictorial Report - Attendance
Administration of Pre-test	Proponent Students	November 2024	- Results of Post-test
Analysis of Results	Proponent	November 2024	- Narrative and Pictorial Report - Attendance
Presentation of Results to School Head	School Head Proponent	December 2024	- Minutes of the Meeting
Accomplishment of Research Output Presentation to District for Possible Adoption of the Material	Proponent PSDS Proponent	December 2024 January-February 2025	- Accomplishment Report - Minutes of the Meeting

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